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PASSIVE HOUSE: FUTURE HOUSE OF VERY LOW ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND ECO-FRIENDLY

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Annotation: Passive house is standard of housing construction, which was started in Europe countries that has both the highest energy efficiency and environmentally friendly. This paper examines the importance of constructing the passive houses, the issues and priorities that need to be addressed to ensure the energy efficiency of buildings and sustainable building.

Today, the Passive House Standard can be implemented in all kinds (types) of buildings almost anywhere around the world. In all climates and for all countries around the world, the goals of passive house are the same. As a result, the problem of building almost self-sufficient buildings (also known as Passive Houses) is well established.

Keywords: passive house, principles, climate, advantages and disadvantages

ПАССИВНЫЙ ДОМ: ДОМ БУДУЩЕГО С НИЗКИМ ЭНЕРГОПОТРЕБЛЕНИЕМ И ЭКОЛОГИЧНОСТЬЮ

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Аннотация: Пассивный дом является стандартом жилищного строительства, которое было начато в странах Европы, которое имеет как самую высокую энергоэффективность, так и экологичность. В настоящем

документе рассматривается важность строительства пассивных домов, вопросы и приоритеты, которые необходимо решить для обеспечения энергоэффективности зданий и устойчивого строительства.

Сегодня стандарт пассивного дома может быть реализован во всех видах (типах) зданий практически в любой точке мира. Во всех климатических условиях и для всех стран мира цели пассивного дома одинаковы. В результате проблема строительства почти самодостаточных зданий (также известных как пассивные дома) хорошо известна.

Ключевые слова: пассивный дом, принципы, климат, преимущества и недостатки

Introduction.

With the current situation of climate change, one of the most pressing issues is related to the environmentally energy use in residential and public buildings, so the use energy-saving resources and other modern energy-saving materials are becoming current materials in several. Building projects all over the world. Such materials can allow not only the reduction the costs for heating or cooling, electricity, hot or cold-water supply and other aspects of modern comfortable housing. In that respect, the technology of a passive house should be considered as a house constructing project with zero energy consumption, which can ensure an environmental standard also high standard condition for habitat. It should be noted that passive houses can be considered not only in general plan, but also in the separate region, from moderately continental climate, cold winters, rain seasons or warm summers.

In the mid-1980s, Sweden and Denmark have made the codes of building that obligatory for all new buildings corresponding to the standard of low energy buildings [1-8]. At that time specialists had ideas of how to improve and develop the principles of low energy buildings, which are: thermal insulation, tightness, and thermal bridge reduction, performance of high quality of windows and doors as well as controlled ventilation system.

The first passive house history was built in 1991 in German with the support of the federal state of Hesse in Darmstadt, Kranichstein [HMUE-a]. The authors of the architectural part of the project are architects prof. Bott-Ridder and Westermayer; the development and implementation of the project was led by Dr. Wolfgang Veits, who at that time was still working at the Institute for Housing and the Environment. The building was completely built in 1991 and since October 1991 four families have been living in it. This building needs so little heat that a separate heating system could actually be dispensed with heating costs are less than 1 liter of oil per year per 1 m² of living space.

Conception of Passive house.

Passive House known as “passivhaus” in German is a building standard that relies on a combination of energy efficiency with passive solar and internal heat gains to dramatically reduce space heating demands and allow for simplified methods of providing needed heat that seen on figure 1. A passive house is an energy-efficient building where the minimum energy use can be combined with a comfortable microclimate.

It is possible to save energy resources by means of innovations. They have to

be justified from an economic point of view, feasible from a technical point of view parties and should not change the habitual way of life of people, and at the same time should comply with environmental and social requirements.

Figure 1 – Passive house

The Passive House is a sustainable building idea that offers low-cost, high-quality structures as well as comfortable, healthy living environments.

1. Passive houses require less than 15 kWh/(m²yr) for heating or cooling.
2. The heating/cooling load is limited to a maximum of 10 W/m².
3. Traditional primary energy use is limited to 120 kWh/(m²a), while renewable energy supply (PER) with a limit of 60 kWh/(m²a) is the way of the future. This is simple to achieve with passive houses.

4. Passive houses must be airtight with air change rates being limited to $n_{50} = 0.6/h$.

5. In warmer climates and/or during summer months, excessive temperatures may not occur more than 10 % of the time.

Principles of Passive House.

The essence of a passive house is to save already 80 % of energy on operating costs only with the help of appropriate architectural design, as well as the use of a controlled supply and exhaust ventilation system with recuperation. Passive house principles are energy-saving house without heating .The basic design principles for a passive house are the following that shown on the figure 2.

Figure 2 – Principles of passive house

Thermal Bridge Reduction Design or No thermal bridging.

Thermal bridges (fig. 3) sometimes known as “cold bridges” in the building envelope have a measurable impact on energy efficiency and thermal comfort. On structures that are not adequately insulated, the impact can be minimal. This entails ensuring that all walls, floors, and roofs are well insulated with no gaps. This cuts down on the amount of heating or cooling required to maintain a pleasant temperature. Reducing thermal bridging at this connection involves positioning the window to line up with the insulation layer, over insulating in front of the frame, and minimizing how far closure flashings penetrate the rough opening while still maintaining adequate drainage paths. Thermal bridging is eliminated or minimized in Passive House projects to ensure the envelope's efficacy in decreasing space-heating energy demand.

Figure 3 – Thermal bridges

Thermal Insulation or High-quality insulation.

Thermal insulation (fig. 4) is an important technology to reduce energy consumption in buildings by preventing heat gain/loss through the building envelope. The quality of the insulation is the key to the success of the building design. The insulation serves to minimize the heat exchange with the outside environment. Thermal insulation is a construction material with low thermal conductivity, often less than 0.1W/m^2 . These materials have no other purpose than to save energy and protect and provide comfort to occupants.

Passive House makes the most of the envelope by super insulating the building to reduce the heat loss. For a Passive House, the aim is to use assemblies with enough insulation to double or triple the heat resistance compared to what is required in current Canadian building codes. The result is a significant increase in the thermal performance expected from the building envelope. The building envelope is what separates the interior of the building from the exterior; it consists of outside walls, roofs, and floors. To reduce this heat loss, insulation made of low-conductivity materials is installed within the wall and roof assemblies [2].

Figure 4 – Thermal Insulation

Passive house windows or superior windows.

To ensure that the entire building envelope is well insulated it is important to use quality windows that have a low thermal conductivity (fig. 5). Passive Houses make efficient use of the sun, internal heat sources and heat recovery. The ‘U value’ is a measure of the window or door’s overall level of conductivity the ability to keep heat inside and cold out [3]. When the U value is lower, the performance and insulation properties of the window are higher. For example, on a $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ winter day, the glass temperature of a high-performance window will remain steady at $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, avoiding unwanted heat loss and expensive heating bills.

Passive House designs take advantage of free passive heating from the sun. Solar heat gain through appropriately placed windows can help offset the amount of heat a building need during colder months. During the summer months, this needs to be act against with shading to prevent too much heat from the sun coming into the building, causing overheating. For each Passive House project, there will be an ideal number of windows that can balance the advantage of free

heat from the sun with minimizing the heat loss from having too many windows [4].

Figure 5 – Passive house windows

Air tightness of Building or Airtight construction.

There should be no uncontrolled airflow between the internal and external environment. Passive Houses allow for space heating and cooling related energy savings. The huge energy savings have been demonstrated in warm climates where typical buildings also require active cooling [3]. Airtight (fig. 6) construction on a Passive House project will further reduce space-heating costs and localized condensation problems and will provide better comfort inside the building. In a Passive House building these advantages cannot be achieved by tightening the building envelope alone but must be coupled with a suitable ventilation strategy to deal with excess humidity in the building.

Figure 6 – Air tightness

Adequate ventilation strategy or Mechanical ventilation with heat recovery.

All of the efforts to insulate the building are complemented by high-quality ventilation that recovers heat from the utilized air and transfers it to the fresh air entering the structure. The key to optimal indoor air quality and energy

savings is efficient heat recovery ventilation. A Passive House ventilation system (fig. 7) uses a heat recovery ventilator (HRV) to continuously remove stale or moist air and deliver fresh air. The process of enhancing interior air quality without opening windows or doors is known as mechanical ventilation with heat recovery (MVHR). It doesn't imply that windows and doors can't be opened; it just means that they don't have to be in order to get fresh air. Although MVHR systems are designed to control indoor air quality rather than to heat or cool buildings, they do recapture warm and cool air that would otherwise be wasted. They also assist in the purification of the air and the regulation of humidity.

Figure 7 – Passive House ventilation system

Different climates zones and climate change adaptation.

Passive House doesn't matter how the climate zone condition or geographical region is, they stay at a comfortable temperature around year with minimal energy inputs. Those buildings are heated "passively", making efficient use of the sun, internal heat sources and heat recovery so that conventional heating systems are rendered unnecessary throughout even the coldest of winters. During warmer months, Passive Houses make use of passive cooling techniques such as strategic shading to keep comfortably cool. Either way, a Passive House's high-quality insulation keeps the temperature comfortable, just where it is needed [3].

The physical equations are the same – only the boundary conditions vary. Thus the solution method can well be applied independently of the circumstances in order to find the appropriate way of Passive House design in a specific country and climate [4]. The software was originally developed with a focus of optimizing the energy efficiency of residential buildings in cool-temperate climates where the space heating demand is dominant and summer comfort is less of a concern.

Advantages and Disadvantages of passive houses.

Advantages of passive houses.

Passive homes are built to an extremely high standard in a bid to make them take as little energy as possible to heat them in winter and cool them in the summer [7]. And as we know the costs budget utilities such as electricity, water

and gas, which can add an additional hundreds of dollars on top of other monthly housing expenses:

1. Energy cost savings and environmental benefits or environment-friendly.
2. Superior acoustic insulation and temperature control.
3. Higher air quality passive.
4. Good for your health.
5. Peace and quiet.

Disadvantages of passive houses.

The passive houses have many benefits or advantages, but they also have some disadvantages to building them:

1. The main disadvantage to building a passive house is the upfront cost.
2. The other disadvantages of passive house its design it can be implemented to optimal standards only in new construction.

Conclusion.

In this context it has proved its worth in thousands of successful building projects. Meanwhile, the Passive House concept is also being applied in hotter and more humid climates, where the energy demand for cooling becomes more important than space heating. While passive houses offer many solutions, both relating to the economy as they allow reducing the high cost of energy per year; to the sustainable development of countries as they are environmentally friendly and can spearhead the sustainable development of countries. However, their implement in countries should be well studied as the cost-effectiveness needs to be assessed before their implementations.

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